

1

Cooling – making efficient choices White paper update 2016

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Abstract

Due to the increasing role of energy costs and growing heat density of servers, cooling issues are becoming highly challenging and very important. While power consumption is recognised to be one of the main challenges for future HPC systems, attention to this issue tends to be limited to the power consumed by the computer hardware only, leaving aside the increase in cooling power required by more densely packaged, highly integrated hardware. The information presented herein is a result of data analysed and collected in a process of distributing a detailed survey among PRACE partners. The PRACE 3IP Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) contributes to the development of energy efficient HPC technologies and architecture, targeting improved cooling and energy efficiency of the overall system along with fine scale monitoring of energy consumption. The methodology designed for this PCP to evaluate energy efficiency could be re-used for other HPC infrastructure procurements, allowing for a better view of the TCO of the future system. This paper provides an overview of traditional technologies cooling and devices currently used in modern HPC data centres as well as some innovative and promising solutions adopted by some PRACE partners that may pave the way for future standards. The advantages and disadvantages of each described solution are discussed and general recommendations are provided as to which aspects HPC centres should take into account when selecting and building a cooling system.

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Abstract	1
Introduction	3
1. State of the art technologies.....	3
1.1. Cooling approaches within the data centre.....	4
1.1.1. Air cooling	4
Open delivery (plenum cooling)	4
Directly coupled solutions.....	4
1.1.2. Liquid cooling	7
Closed loop water cooling	7
Direct water cooling	7
Indirect (Hybrid) Air/Water Cooling	7
1.1.3. Discussion	7
1.2. Heat rejection from the data centre.....	10
1.2.1. Self-contained air-cooled unit.....	10
1.2.2. Air-cooled system with direct expansion refrigeration (DX).....	10
1.2.3. Glycol cooling systems.....	10
1.2.4. Water cooled systems	10
1.2.5. Chilled water systems.....	10
1.2.6. Economizers	11
1.2.7. Using naturally occurring sources of cold water for free cooling	12
1.2.8. Geothermal exchange.....	13
1.2.9. Adsorption Refrigeration.....	13
2. Cooling results of the survey.....	14
2.1. Please describe basics of your DLC machine.....	14
2.2. Cooling solution: The internal part	14
2.3. Cooling solution: Infrastructure part: DLC but also other e.g. Rear-Door cooled solutions	15
2.4. Lessons learned. The knowledge gained during commissioning operation of the machine... 15	
2.5. Anything new in the air-cooling that you got your hands on during the last two years?	15
3. Conclusions	16
4. Recommendations.....	17
Acknowledgements.....	17

Introduction

This document is one in a series produced by the PRACE project partners that aim to discuss key major aspects of designing and running a modern HPC data centre such as cooling, energy management, location issues, and reliability. In this paper, we focus on the topic of cooling which, due to the increasing role of energy costs and growing heat density of servers, is becoming one of the most challenging issues. Depending on the installed cooling equipment and servers, the energy that has to be spent on dissipating the heat from the servers can be as high as 40% (Figure 1) of the total power budget.

Figure 1 Distribution of power consumed in a Data Centre^h Terms used are explained in the following sections

This document looks at different methods used for Data Centre IT equipment and rooms and highlights the pros and cons of each solution. The intended audience of this document are people involved in the design of a new Data Centre or the refurbishment of an existing one. The information may be also useful also to persons involved in the selection and acquisition of HPC systems as these are the most challenging ones to cool.

1. State of the art technologies

There are many different devices and cooling technologies used in data centres. There are a few basic elements that are common for all the solutions:

- Heat is removed from its source by means of a cooling medium such as air-, water or glycol for example.
- Pumps or fans ensure the movement of the cooling medium within the cooling loops.
- Heat exchanger units ensure the exchange of energy between the different cooling loops.
- The cooling medium is cooled either by means of a refrigeration process or thanks to a naturally occurring source of cold such as the outside air or a natural water body. The latter is referred to as „free-cooling“.

In this section, we will present the basic strategies for dealing with heat inside the data centre, whilst section 1.2 will discuss the different approaches for dissipating heat from the data centre to the outside environment.

^h Source: Implementing Efficient Data Centers: http://www.climateactionprogramme.org/images/uploads/documents/NRAN-6LXSHX_R1_EN_-_schneider_electric.pdf

1.1. Cooling approaches within the data centre

Heat management in a data centre requires careful selection of the cooling technologies. A few general solutions for heat management in the computer room have evolved over the time. For the purpose of this paper we will build on the definitions used by ASHRAE technical committee (TC) 9.9¹ for the different cooling approaches:

Air cooling

- Open delivery (plenum cooling)
- Directly coupled solutions (involving some form of containment)
 - Hot or cold aisle containment
 - Chimney or front plenum
 - Rear door heat exchanger (RDHX) or side car (also defined as hybrid cooling)

Liquid cooling

- Water internal to IT system (closed loop water cooling)
- Water external to IT system with internal or external Coolant Distribution Unit (CDU)
 - Direct water cooling
 - Indirect (Hybrid) Air/Water Cooling

1.1.1. Air cooling

Open delivery (plenum cooling)

The open delivery cooling system is currently still the most used. For this approach, Computer Room Air Conditioning (CRAC) units usually emit cold air under the raised floor from where it is directed towards IT equipment via perforated tiles or grates located in front of the racks. The hot air that is exhausted from the IT systems flows back to the CRAC units, where it is once again cooled by means of gas or chilled water. This setup can comprise a dropped ceiling for the return air. It allows for a flexible organization of the racks within the data centre and continues to be the preferred solution for low density environments. However, it does not cope well with rack densities in excess of 15kW per rack that have become pervasive in the HPC environment in recent years. This is due to the inefficiency generated by the mixing of hot and cold air and the need for very high airflows due to the limited thermal capacity of air. Due to the small temperature gradient between the coolant and air temperatures this approach requires the use of larger heat exchangers.

Directly coupled solutions

The need to accommodate ever-increasing compute power within given computer room footprints and the availability of low-cost x86 servers has led to ever-greater power densities per rack. As a result, rack densities in excess of 30kW are not uncommon in the HPC environment today. The mixing of hot and cold air streams in the open delivery setup discussed above significantly reduces the efficiency of CRAC units. Different equipment within a server room may have different power draws and heat densities, which may cause localised hot spots. Directly coupled cooling systems alleviate this problem by separating the cold and hot air streams. These solutions are discussed below.

Hot or cold aisle containment

An initial step to improving cooling efficiency within the data centre can be achieved by containing either the cold or hot aisles, thereby directly coupling one of the two air streams to the CRAC units and avoiding or at least reducing them mixing. Hot aisle containment may be achieved with baffles that ensure the hot air is conducted directly into the plenum of the dropped ceiling. Cold aisle containment usually involves the formation of “pods” comprising two rows of rack with a central and roofed cold aisle. This method requires the installation of baffles to contain either the hot or cold aisles.

It can be accompanied by localised overhead or in-row cooling units. These localised cooling units support the CRAC units located at the periphery of the data centre.

¹ Source: ASHRAE Datacom Series, „IT Equipment Design Impact on Data Center Solutions, 2016

Chimney or front plenum

This approach is similar to the above described hot or cold aisle containment. It requires the installation of chimneys that conduct hot air directly from the rear side of the racks into the dropped ceiling or air funnels that direct the cold air stream from the raised floor to the front of the rack. Such an approach can be applied to single racks or entire rows. An example is shown in the figures below. This method requires the installation of the chimneys or front plenums and may include fans to assist the movement of air (active) or not (passive).

Figure 2: Server racks with dedicated exhaust chimneys^j

Rear door heat exchanger (RDHX) or side car

By adding rear doors heat exchangers or side cars to each rack, it is possible to remove the waste heat as soon as it exits the rack. This method requires the purchase of RDHX or side cars units and their connection to a cold water supply. These units may include fans to assist the movement of air (active) or not (passive). This form of cooling is also referred to as indirect or hybrid cooling (see section below on indirect air/water cooling). By removing a significant portion of the heat when it exits the rack, RDHXs assist the CRAC units located at the periphery of the data centre.

Discussion

Whilst the open delivery method works well for low density environments, it is suboptimal for high-density environments. For this reason it is common to encounter various flavours of directly coupled solutions in high-density environments. Currently, numerous vendors offer complete solutions comprising ceilings, doors, racks and the monitoring equipment and promise^k energy savings of up to 30%. The use of directly coupled solutions reduces the volume of air that needs to be cooled, but does require the installation of a dedicated cooling loop and the acquisition of the requisite cooling units (RDHX, overhead cooling units or in-row cooling units) that require capital investment and take up additional space in the data centre. In heterogeneous environments it is important that the localised units be well matched to the heat density of the area they support in order to avoid hotspots and overheating. In a heterogeneous area additional care should be taken to ensure creating large pressure differentials that can adversely impact the performance of the IT equipment. A study by ASHRAE shows that this risk is particularly high in directly coupled solutions with passive air movement for high-density environments. When active air movement is in place the risk is considered to be minor. The risk of pressure differentials in hot or cold aisle containment solutions is deemed to be negligible to minor.^l As an external study shows^m, proper planning and strict separation of hot and cold air flows allow air cooling to be used for rack densities of up to 40 kW.

^j Source: <http://powerquality.eaton.com/EMEA/PowerNews/PowerNews-0311/heat-management.asp>

^k <http://www.emersonnetworkpower.com/en-US/Solutions/ByApplication/DataCenterNetworking/SmartSolutions/Documents/SL-11460.pdf>

^l ASHRAE, Datacom Series, „IT Equipment Design Impact on Data Center Solutions“, 2016

^m <http://www.intel.com/it/pdf/air-cooled-data-centers.pdf>

All the above-mentioned approaches may be used not only exclusively but also in conjunction resulting in systems such as the one in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Hot aisle containment with chimneyⁿ

Airflow management within the data centre is not an easy task. A number of different software (e.g. OpenFOAM or COVISE/ANSYS) exist that allow the simulation of different rack arrangements and their impact on the airflow within the data centre. Such simulations are useful as they provide helpful hints on the airflow prior to the installation of hardware or to assist in airflow optimisation. However, the accuracy of the simulation depends heavily on the quality of the input data. Obtaining this can be cost-intensive in real-life scenarios. The following figure shows examples of simulation results, which can be obtained using aforementioned software packages.

Figure 4 Simulation of the air-flow in a data centre room

ⁿ Source: <http://nubissolutions.com/solutions/hot-air-return/>

1.1.2. Liquid cooling

All the solutions mentioned earlier use air as a medium to remove the heat from the servers and are not well suited to high-density environments due to the limited thermal capacity of air. The replacement of air with a liquid cooling medium is a potential source of significant benefits in terms of efficiency as well as facilitating the cooling of higher densities. The various liquid cooling methods are discussed below.

Closed loop water cooling

With this method the cooling loop is entirely contained within the IT system. Heat is removed from the IT components through liquid-cooled plates. The liquid medium then transfers the heat to a system-internal water-to-air heat exchanger. The heated air is exhausted from the IT system by fans pushing air through this water-to-air heat exchanger. This cooling method requires no connection to the facilities cooling loop.

Direct water cooling

With this approach the heat from the IT components is transferred to a liquid cooling medium through liquid-cooled plates. The heat is then transferred to the facility cooling loop via a liquid-to-water heat exchanger. This cooling method requires the facility cooling loop to connect to the cooling distribution (CDU) unit of the IT system.

Indirect (Hybrid) Air/Water Cooling

An alternative way of optimizing cooling is to confine the air-flow within a rack or series of racks. This may be done by coupling the facility cooling loop with cooling units attached to a single rack or multiple racks in the form of in-row units, rear door heat exchangers or side car units. The currently available in-row cooling technology is able to manage up to 60 kW per rack. All flavours of this cooling method require the purchase of the cooling units (RDHX, side cars or in-row coolers) and their connection to the facilities cooling distribution.

1.1.3. Discussion

Whilst air cooling offers maximum flexibility in terms of layout of racks in the data centre, it is not well suited to cope with rack densities in excess of 15kW. For this reason it is common to find different flavours of liquid cooling deployed within HPC environments.

Both direct liquid cooling and hybrid cooling solutions require the deployment of pipework within the datacentre in order to connect the facility cooling loop to the cooling loop of the IT systems. Usually these pipes are installed under the raised floor, where they can obstruct the air-flow and add the potential risk of leakages. On the other hand, these method are more energy-efficient as they requires the movement of significantly less air and there is virtually no mixing of hot and cold air streams. This reduction of air volume does however also provide less thermal inertia. In case of a cooling problem, the temperature inside the rack will rise faster and can lead to servers overheating and emergency shutdown.

Liquid cooling typically yields better energy-efficiency than air cooling as the energy required to pump the cooling medium is significantly less than the energy required to cool the same amount of energy by moving large quantities of air. The thermal capacity of water is also 3500 times greater than that of air and it has significantly better heat transfer capabilities. Operational costs for liquid cooling are lower than for air cooling and when starting from scratch, the investment costs are comparable. Liquid cooled IT systems are generally more compact although their higher weight per rack and potentially proprietary rack form factors can add complexity. The risk of leakages within the racks has rarely been observed and can be contained with proper monitoring. Liquid cooling methods allow the installation of very high density racks.

Traditionally liquid cooled IT systems have worked with inlet water temperatures between 15°C and 25°C. Newer directly liquid cooled systems work with water inlet temperatures of 45°C and more. The ASHRAE “*Liquid Cooling Guidelines for Datacom Equipment Centers*” publication provides a detailed overview of the different temperature classes for liquid cooling systems as well as in depth discussion of topics such as loop isolation, velocity and water

quality. While it is possible to use cold water (<18°C) to drive a direct water cooling loop, the use of warm water^o (>40°C) is favourable for a number of reasons:

- Operating at low temperatures bears the risk of reaching inlet temperatures below the dew point causing condensation within the system.
- If the system is designed for inlet temperatures above 40°C, free-cooling with outside air becomes possible year-round in most geographic regions, eliminating the need for active, compressor-based cooling.
- The ability to effectively re-use the waste heat increases with higher temperatures. Return temperatures starting from 45°C can be used to heat buildings and to drive adsorption chillers. Higher temperatures could potentially allow tri-generation, the combined production of electricity, heating and cooling.

While higher inlet temperatures improve the possibilities for the re-utilisation of waste heat, this benefit needs to be compared against the increases in leakage current and potentially higher component failure rates of the hardware. The two sides of this equation should be carefully evaluated in order to find the sweet spot for optimal IT operation and heat re-utilisation.

The two tables below provide a summary of the advantages and disadvantages of the various cooling methods.

	Air cooling			
	<i>Open delivery (plenum cooling)</i>	<i>Hot or cold aisle containment</i>	<i>Chimney or front plenum</i>	<i>Rear door heat exchanger (RDHX) or side car</i>
Flexibility of equipment placement	Very high; racks can be placed anywhere in the room and easily relocated.	Medium/High; depending on solution used for separation of the hot/cold areas.	Medium-low. Hard to re-arrange the racks once the infrastructure is installed.	Low, similar to rack-chimney or front plenum approach.
Infrastructure complexity	Low, only CRAC units and possibly raised floor for air distribution.	Low-medium, additional infrastructure for separation of hot/cold air required.	Medium; installation of chimneys or front plenums necessary and dropped ceiling required.	Medium/high, direct connectors of chilled water to each cooling unit/rack are required.
Capability	Up to 10-14kW per rack, prone to hot spots at higher densities.	Up to 40 kW per rack when implemented accurately.	Up to 30 kW per rack.	Up to 35 kW per rack.
Energy-efficiency	Low, hot and cold air mix and thus reduce the efficiency of CRAC units.	Medium, a good hot/cold air separation can be achieved but solution still requires a lot of air has to be transported.	Very high if the power inside rack is close to the maximum cooling power, good separation	Very high if the power inside rack is close to the maximum cooling power, good separation
Problems	Hot spots, high energy overheads.	Overheating if imbalanced fan power, hot spots still possible.	Coordination with other overhead distributions necessary.	Overheating if imbalanced fan power, hot spots still possible.

Table 1 Summary air cooling methods

^o See ASHRAE 2011 Thermal Guidelines for Liquid Cooled Data Processing Environments for water temperature classification

	Liquid cooling		
	<i>Closed loop water cooling</i>	<i>Direct water cooling</i>	<i>Indirect (Hybrid) Air/Water Cooling</i>
Flexibility of equipment placement	Very high; possible to re-arrange the racks at will.	Medium-low; racks can be placed wherever the facility cooling loop can be extended to. Re-arranging racks is complex due to the dedicated piping.	Medium-low. racks can be placed anywhere the facility cooling loop can be extended to. Re-arranging racks is complex due to the dedicated piping.
Infrastructure complexity	Simple, only CRAC units and possibly raised floor for air distribution.	High, requires a dedicated cooling distribution to the racks or the CDUs in addition to coolant ducts inside server or rack.	High, requires a dedicated cooling distribution to the cooling units.
Capability	Medium, up to ~20 kW	Very high, up to 100 kW per rack	High, up to 60 kW per rack.
Energy-efficiency	High, good separation of hot and cold streams.	Very high. Increased possibility to re-use waste heat.	Very high if the power inside the rack is matched to the available cooling power, very good separation of hot and cold streams.
Problems	Risk of gas leaks.	Leak risk; very little thermal inertia in case of failure of the cooling system.	Overheating if imbalanced fan power, hot spots still possible.

Table 2: Summary liquid cooling methods

1.2. Heat rejection from the data centre

In the previous section, we discussed how to dissipate heat generated by the IT equipment inside the data centre. In order to provide a complete picture, the next section focuses on how this heat is then rejected from the data centre to the outside environment. The following section provides an overview of the five most commonly found methods for removing heat from the data centre based on a classification by APC.^P

1.2.1. Self-contained air-cooled unit

This method consists in units containing condensing coils located around the perimeter or within the dropped ceiling of the data centre. These units take in the warm air from the data centre and run it over the condensing coil, subsequently exhausting hot air at around 49°C that must be ducted away from the data centre and is usually exhausted outside the building. The evacuated air must be replaced with outside air in order to avoid creating negative pressure within the data centre. This method generates very low installation costs that are limited to the units themselves and the ducting and/or dropped ceiling. The capacity per unit of this solution is limited to around 15kW.

1.2.2. Air-cooled system with direct expansion refrigeration (DX)

This method consists of Computer Room Air Conditioning (CRAC) units located around the perimeter or within the data centre space and air cooled condenser units that are usually located on the data centre roof. Warm air from the data centre is drawn into the top of the CRAC unit and pulled down through a set of evaporator coils. The compressor that supplies the liquid refrigerant for the cooling process is located within the CRAC unit. The refrigerant loop extends to the condenser unit on the roof, whence it evacuates the heat to the external environment. This method benefits from lowest overall cost and low maintenance requirements. For energy efficiency reasons the distance between the CRAC units and the condenser unit should not exceed 20m.

1.2.3. Glycol cooling systems

This method is similar to the afore-described air-cooled DX system. However, with this method, the refrigerant loop is limited to the inside of the CRAC, whilst a heat exchanger unit allows the heat from the refrigerant loop to be passed to the separate glycol loop that extends to a fluid cooler unit that is typically located on the roof of the data centre. The glycol loop has the advantage that it can be efficiently run over greater distances than the refrigerant loop of the air-cooled DX method. It does however have higher installation costs.

1.2.4. Water cooled systems

Similarly to the previous two, this method also uses CRAC units within the data centre. In the water cooled method the glycol loop has been replaced by a water loop that runs between the heat exchanger unit in the CRAC unit and the roof-top cooling tower. Having extracted the heat from the CRAC unit the water is sprayed onto the surfaces within the cooling tower. The evaporation of a part of the water extracts energy from the remaining water, thereby cooling it. This evaporation process is aided by fans. The water loop can be efficiently run over greater distances but the installation costs are significantly higher. This system also has higher maintenance costs as it requires continuous water treatment and cleaning of the cooling towers.

1.2.5. Chilled water systems

With the chiller-based cooling method, the heat is extracted from the data centre by circulating the warm air through Computer Room Air Handler (CRAH) units that are located around the perimeter or within the data centre space. Contrary to the CRAC unit that contains the refrigeration cycle, the CRAH unit only contains a chilled water coil, which extracts the heat from the data centre air. This coil is fed with chilled water from the building's mechanical plant where the chiller unit is typically located. The chilled water loop runs between the coil in the CRAH and the chiller unit. The

^P America Power Conversion (2004), White Paper #59, „The Different Types of Air Conditioning Equipment for IT Environments“, Rev. 2004-0, <http://www.apcdistributors.com/white-papers/Cooling/WP-59%20The%20Different%20Types%20of%20Air%20Conditioning%20Equipment%20for%20IT%20Environments.pdf>

chiller extracts the heat from the chilled water loop by means of its evaporator heat exchanger and transfers it to a separate outside cooling loop by means of its condenser heat exchanger. The outside cooling loop runs from the chiller to the rooftop cooling tower where the heat is rejected by means of the same evaporation process described in the previous method. Of all the methods described this is the most expensive in terms of initial installation costs. For large installations it generates the lowest operational costs and it offer comparatively higher reliability.

1.2.6. Economizers^q

In sufficiently cool climates, economizers can be used to reduce the amount of mechanical cooling required. This can be done by bringing cold outside air directly into the data centre or by using the cold outside air to extract heat from a refrigerant or water cooling loop. Depending on the average outside temperature and humidity of a given location, economizers can reduce the power used by the cooling system by 30 to 50%. The two most commonly used economizers are discussed in this section. This approach is frequently also referred to as free cooling which can be misleading, as while it reduces the operational costs, all the other parts of the cooling system such as pumps, fans, etc. continue to work.

Fluid economizers

This type of economizer is used in conjunction with chilled water or glycol cooling systems.

With glycol cooling systems this is usually done by running the glycol loop through an economizer coil within the CRAC unit when outside temperatures are low enough. This allows the refrigerant cycle to be switched off, thereby reducing the amount of energy consumed for the cooling process. This approach is also referred to as Indirect Free Cooling (IFC).

With chilled water systems an economizer setup may use drycoolers or cooling towers on the roof. When outside temperatures are low enough, these will reduce the load on the chiller. The higher the required output temperature from the chiller the more the economizer hours will be increased.

Water-cooled systems display a significantly higher Coefficient of Performance (COP)^r, compared with the air-cooled systems and IFC systems are more energy-efficient compared to conventional systems. However, the exact values depend on the climate conditions and the operating temperature in the computer room. The dependency on the climate can be reduced by increasing the working temperature of the water (or glycol) or using a source of naturally cold water such as a river, lake or sea instead of air as the heat recipient.

IFC also improves the Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE), hence providing a more sustainable cooling solution for data centres. The increased COP also means this method requires less floor space compared with the air-cooled chiller solutions. A possible disadvantage of IFC is the higher initial cost compared to the conventional cooling solutions. However, as the exact benefits and costs may be influenced by the local climate and vendor, a case-specific analysis should be conducted.

Air economizers

This type of economizer uses outside air directly to cool or control the temperature in the data centre. To this end sensors allow air inlets to open and let outside air into the data centre when the outside temperature is sufficiently low. This temporarily or, depending on the climate, completely reduces the need for air conditioning. Exhaust air dampers allow the surplus air to exit the data centre. This solution is often referred to as Direct Free Cooling (DFC). Figure 5 below illustrates this method.

^q Thermalogic (April 2014), „Economizers Fundamentals: Smart Approaches to Energy-Efficient, Economizer Usage for Data Centers“, <http://www.thermalnews.com/main/articles/economizer-fundamentals-smart-approaches-to-energy-efficient-economizer-usage-for-data-centers/>

^r http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Coefficient_of_performance

Figure 5: Direct Air Cooling

This method is theoretically the most efficient way of air-cooling, but one has to address possible challenges that come with this technology. First of all its usefulness is determined by the local climate. Both temperature and humidity must be adequate for this approach to work efficiently. To use DFC, data centre building must be designed in a specific way as the air ducts may require significant space. Another possible disadvantage of DFC is the risk of bringing gaseous contaminants into the data centre and the possibility of higher humidity levels within the data centre. These systems also require significant maintenance and are not well suited for high-density environments. Whilst the use of DFC can significantly reduce operational costs, it usually requires full back-up in the form of conventional cooling to take over from the free cooling when the outside temperature is too high. In order for DFC to be a viable solution for cooling, climate and temperature studies need to be conducted for the location of the data centre.

1.2.7. Using naturally occurring sources of cold water for free cooling

Depending on the data centre's geographical location it may be possible to use a naturally occurring source of cold water to cool the data centre. Depending on the temperature of this water source, a chiller may not be necessary at all or may only be necessary to make up the difference in temperature, thus consuming significantly less energy. The cold water source can either be tapped with an open cooling loop or by placing the coils of a closed cooling loop in or below the body of water. (Figure 6).

Figure 6 Using closed cooling loop coils with water body⁵

By replacing the air with water as a heat receiver, the total power consumption of the data centre may be reduced by more than 20% (see Figure 1), as there is no need for chillers or fans on the dry cooler units.

⁵ Source: <http://www.neutralexistence.com/begreen/geothermal-exchange-ground-source-heating-and-cooling/>

1.2.8. Geothermal exchange

Geothermal ground-source heating and cooling, technically known as geothermal exchange, is the process of harnessing the earth's constant underground temperature to heat or cool a building. Compared to above ground air temperatures that can vary between sub-zero and over 40°C the earth's temperature two meters below the surface remains relatively constant and only varies between 10°C and 20°C. Thanks to this it is possible to use the geothermal exchange to reject or extract heat from the ground. In order to dissipate 1kW of heat one would need to place approximately 35 to 50 m of pipe length at 2.5 meters under the ground.

The potential savings are similar to those seen when using naturally occurring cold water sources but the need for substantial underground pipelines makes it difficult to scale the cooling system if the installation grows.

It is also possible to use high-temperature geothermal water to produce chilled water using tri-generation¹. This, however, requires high-grade heat and therefore its applicability is limited by the availability of a source of high temperature water. A careful environmental study should be conducted prior to installing such a system in order to ensure that it does not adversely impact the ground water ecosystem or drinking water supply.

1.2.9. Adsorption Refrigeration

Adsorption refrigeration allows the thermal energy of waste heat to be used for cooling purposes. Instead of dissipating waste heat to ambient air or a natural source of cold water, its entropy can be used to generate chilled water with almost no additional energy. The basic working principle is as follows: a refrigerant, usually water, is adsorbed and desorbed by a solid adsorbent such as silica gel or zeolite. During this process, the refrigerant changes its state of matter four times – from gas to liquid and back. Three water loops of different temperature levels are required to drive the process: high temperature (HT, >45°C), medium temperature (MT, ~25°C), and low temperature (LT, <20°C). The cooling process then happens in 2 phases:

In the first phase the waste heat is fed into the HT loop and used to heat the adsorbent and thereby desorb the refrigerant. The evaporated refrigerant condenses at a condenser driven by the MT loop. In a second phase, once the refrigerant has been fully desorbed, it is vaporized in a vacuum by an evaporator driven by the LT loop. The evaporated refrigerant is then adsorbed by the adsorbent and the heat energy produced by this phase change is removed by the MT loop.

The phase change of the refrigerant from liquid to gas in phase 2 removes heat from the LT loop to facilitate the evaporation. As it takes place in a vacuum, this evaporation process can be driven by very low temperatures and hence can lower the temperature in the LT loop to levels well below 20°C. To allow for continuous operation, commercial adsorption chillers encompass two separate adsorbent chambers so both phases can take place concurrently. The MT loop connects to the external heat exchangers, i.e. the dry-/wet-coolers. The efficiency of the process improves the greater the temperature difference between the HT loop and the MT loop. With the temperature levels mentioned above, the process is already quite efficient and reaches COP values of 1:20.

When looking at the performance of adsorption refrigeration, there are three different coefficients of performance (COP) that should be taken into account: the thermal COP, the electrical COP, and the total COP. The thermal COP describes the ratio of heat energy fed into the adsorption chiller and the cold generated. Latest generation adsorption chillers reach a thermal COP of up to 0.5, i.e. 50% of the heat energy is transformed into cold. While this may not sound impressive, one has to consider that adsorption chilling allows the recovery of 50% of the energy from what would normally have been waste heat.

The electrical COP accounts for the electrical energy required to generate cold. Adsorption refrigeration itself does not require any electrical energy to happen. However, the pumps and valves required to move the water in the three loops consume electrical energy. The actual amount obviously depends on the respective environment and setup, but typical electrical COP values are in the range 1:5 to 1:10. Most of this electrical energy would have been consumed regardless of the actual cooling technology deployed in order to move the waste heat and cold.

¹ <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Trigeneration>

The total COP accounts for the cold generated as well as the total heat removed, i.e. the sum of heat removed from the HT loop and cold fed into the LT loop. The total COP relates this energy with the electrical energy consumed. Latest generation adsorption chillers reach total COP values of around 1:20, putting them on a par with direct free cooling.

2. Cooling results of the survey

In order to get the picture of what the current status in the European HPC centres is and what changed since the last whitepaper was issued, a survey was conducted among the PRACE partners. The information gathered from 9 different centres allowed us to create an overview of cooling technologies used by large supercomputer installations. Results presented below are by no means complete but give an overview on which cooling technologies are used and how the adoption of newer approaches is progressing as well as what kind of results can be expected.

The following presents a summary of the collected results.

2.1. Please describe basics of your DLC machine

In order to be able to assess what changed since the last edition of the whitepaper we asked partner HPC centres to describe their new machines. Directly cooled systems were of special interest as using this approach was one of the recommendations included in the last white paper.

All reported machines have a theoretical peak performance of more than 1 PFlops, the majority between 1.5 and 2 PFlops with the largest one of 5.9 PFlops. Power consumed by the machines varied from 0.5 to 2 MW and, with the exception of Cray machine, they cool their heat generating components (CPU, memory etc.) directly with water. The majority of the systems were installed in 2014 and 2015, one machine was installed in 2012 and one is in the process of being deployed. Seven systems are equipped with the Intel Xeon processors gen. v2 and v3, two systems are equipped with GPGPU or Phi accelerators.

2.2. Cooling solution: The internal part

In all but one case the cooling solution provided by the vendor of the machine was adopted. The one exception is a Huawei system that was retrofitted with vendor permission following a prior smaller scale installation. There was no implementation using liquids other than water. It seems that, despite potential benefits, no one is willing to use more or less experimental technology (like submersion cooling) in large-scale deployments. Out of eight machines that use a DLC solution, only one system only cools the CPUs with water, while the other systems cool at least the CPUs and memory chips. The systems are reported to be 80% room neutral; therefore some traditional air cooling is still needed to supplement the more efficient, direct liquid cooling. Installation and deployment of a large DLC machine seems to be comparable with an air-cooled system. Only in one case the deployment reportedly took twice as long as with a traditional machine. It seems that vendors handle the additional complexity related to the cooling loop well so it usually does not affect the deployment time.

A few years ago, when first DLC machines were installed, coolant chemistry and purity was regarded an important issue that may impact the operation of the machine. All sites report that these topics are acknowledged and addressed by vendors and— where necessary - a monitoring or purification system is installed. Also, the additional potential maintenance effort required by the DLC loop that was foreseen few in 2012 is addressed by the vendors in a way that does not really impact the supercomputer usage.

The risk of leaks that was considered a major concern is also addressed by the solution providers: a leak detection system is a common element with some cooling loops detecting anomalies by observing coolant properties (e.g. pressure) or allow for visual inspection.

2.3. Cooling solution: Infrastructure part: DLC but also other e.g. Rear-Door cooled solutions

Please describe your DC infrastructure that supports your system

In order to reap maximum energy efficiency benefits from a DLC system it is desirable to have a separate cooling loop that can operate at higher temperatures (ASHRAE W3-W5: 25-45°C and more) than those usually utilized for the facility chilled loop (6-18°C). Six out of the nine centres have a dedicated loop for the warm water-cooling. The coolant temperature in the warm water loop only exceeds 35°C in one case and even in this single case it is 40°C. These cooling loops would therefore be considered a W3 classification according to ASHRAE .

Despite the fact that in eight out of nine cases the facility side of the DLC cooling loop was partially or exclusively built for the computer, the related infrastructure installation costs, whenever it was possible to extract these from the total cost of the machine, were not a significant portion of the entire budget: 5% maximum. There is, however, huge disproportion of the duration of preparing the facility for the machine. Installation time required to build or adjust the facility for the system ranged from a couple of weeks to one year. This huge spread is probably caused by different intensity and scope of work in different sites determined by the installation schedule and existing infrastructure.

The pPUE^u of the system connected to the DLC varies between 1.1 and 1.3 so it is significantly better than air cooled solutions. In one case a big variation between PUE was stated: 1.18 during winter and 1.68 during summer. This can be explained by the fact that the water temperature varied between 18 and 25°C, taking into account the placement of the supercomputer centre (southern Europe) means that, most probably, during the summer days the cooling loop is not able to keep the coolant under 25°C without using compressors. Worse pPUE value is caused by the additional energy consumed by the chillers.

2.4. Lessons learned. The knowledge gained during commissioning operation of the machine

The main reason for the acquisition of a DLC machine, cited by seven out of nine sites, was the aim to reduce the operational costs of the machine. Other motivations that were pointed out were: reduction of carbon footprint, physical size of the machine, energy re-use and the pursuit of a sustainable supercomputer infrastructure. In one case the use of DLC was a direct result of the type of supercomputer as there was no option for an air-cooled version. It turns out that installing a DLC machine poses no special risks or challenges. The main issues mentioned regard the decisions related to the precise sizing and placement of the pipes. Also, in line with the answers to previous questions, vendors and integrators prepared the deployment procedures well. The only issues mentioned are small problems related to fine tuning of the cooling loops. The deployment of DLC machines introduces a learning curve for both the integrators and the data centre operators. Small issues were reported in the deployment phase or human errors in handling the cooling loop that resulted in an unscheduled partial shutoff of the machine. No major problems were pointed out but there were some minor issues related to staff training, especially in the first phase of deployment and system operation. The overall reliability of the DLC system is at least equal to the traditional air-cooling, with one answer suggesting that it is better than air-cooling.

2.5. Anything new in the air-cooling that you got your hands on during the last two years?

According to the answers, no new technologies for data centre cooling have become available since the last edition of the white paper. There are predictions that DLC will become a mainstream in HPC in the foreseeable future. There are a few alternative solutions in different stages of market readiness (phase-change cooling, different coolants, various implementations of immersion cooling) but so far the conservative solution seems to be dominating the market. If any of the alternative solutions prove themselves to offer customers or vendors significant benefits this may change.

^u As the PUE term is relating to the whole data center, partial PUE (pPUE) in this documents relates to the efficiency of the machine and the equipment needed by the machine

3. Conclusions

In the time period between the first release of the white paper and this update, data centre cooling technology has not change significantly. This is not surprising though, as data centres are typically designed to operate for many years (15-20) and modifications are usually implemented conservatively. In supercomputing the cost of energy has become a significant factor and therefore a lot of emphasis was put on the energy efficiency of new supercomputers resulting in more systems with direct liquid cooling (DLC). This trend was predicted in the last iteration of this white paper and the guidelines for building new data centres have been extended to cover the requirements of such machines.

At the time of writing the first white paper in 2012, DLC was considered an experimental technology, despite fact that some companies like Cray (e.g. Cray 2 machine in 1985) used to deliver liquid cooled systems in the past, and there were many unknown risks related to this technology. Since then a significant percentage of newly installed supercomputers (in fact in all centres that responded to the questionnaire and installed new machines) are being cooled directly with liquid so it is possible to gather the experiences and present which dangers and benefits are related with employing this technology.

DLC does not increase the cost of big machines or their complexity. As there are no standards regarding the cooling solutions of really big installations, in most cases the installation of a new supercomputer forces some adjustments in the cooling and power infrastructure regardless of whether it is a DLC solution or not.

DLC systems provide cost advantages when applied to sufficiently large machines. Using coolant at temperatures above 20°C increases the benefits in terms of energy savings, due to an increased number of free cooling hours, and improves the potential for waste heat re-use. The advantages and drawbacks of a DLC installation should be assessed on a case by case basis taking into account existing data centre infrastructure, IT system characteristics and local climate.

DLC is mostly used to lower PUE and thereby reduce the cost of cooling. Depending on the local climate, 30-40°C inlet temperature of the coolant seems to be enough to reap benefits in terms of reduced energy bills. If operating temperatures do not allow for year-round chiller-free operation a chiller support is necessary and thus reduced the overall energy efficiency of the solution and increasing ROI. Regardless of the temperature range, liquid cooling offers advantages in terms of packing density and increased potential for heat re-use that, in some cases, may be more important than OPEX savings.

The biggest problem raised, when talking about using liquids to cool the servers, is the danger of leaks. This issue seems to be well addressed by the system vendors. Every system has built-in mechanism for leak detection and/or damage reduction.

As the coolant loop extends to inside the servers, the usual split of competence between infrastructure operators and system operators is no longer possible. Additional competence is required for both teams as the computers behave differently than traditional HVAC units on one hand. On the other hand, system administrators have to understand how the cooling works and have to monitor the coolant and part of the cooling loop as it became part of the supercomputer.

4. Recommendations

Based on the collective experience of different partner organisations in operating current HPC centres and the challenges they foresee in accommodating future supercomputing systems, we have compiled the following list of recommendations that should be taken into consideration during the process of designing a new cooling infrastructure or upgrading an existing one:

- Try to use direct water-cooling for the high-density (more than 10 kW/rack) systems.
- Include additional cooling loops for hot water-cooling in your facility whenever you are designing a new HPC centre.
- If forced by external conditions (old building etc.) to use air-cooling, use hot and cold air separation techniques.
- Try to exploit the benefits of the geographical localization of your data centre: cool climate, lake or river in close vicinity, hot water reuse in the city centre, etc.
- When using direct water-cooling try to employ a system that allows for operation at temperatures above 40° Celsius. This will simplify your cooling system, make it more efficient, reliable, and improve the options for heat re-use.
- Currently, there is no single good solution for all IT equipment and there is a trade-off between flexibility of air-cooling solutions and the energy efficiency of liquid-cooled solutions. Make sure to consider the most efficient choice for each class of IT equipment within your centre.
- When buying new systems, consider asking for the pPUE of the machine that includes all data centre equipment that will be needed to run the system (e.g. chilled water generators etc.) to be at most 1.1.
- Whenever possible, use cost of ownership-related metrics, including at least costs of power and cooling for a predicted period of use of the new building or supercomputer in addition to acquisition and maintenance cost. TCO metrics will be more accurate if including evaluation of production codes, such as the ones from the UEABS^v benchmarks suite. A good set of recommendations that may be considered during procurement can be found: https://eehpcwg.llnl.gov/documents/compsys/aa_procurement_2014.pdf
- High temperature cooling increases the potential for heat re-use and is more cost-effective. Re-using heat may reduce the operation costs of the entire data centre and, may make the switch to DLC even more cost-effective.

Acknowledgements

This work was financially supported by the PRACE project, partly funded by the Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) under Grant Agreement No. 653838.

^v www.prace-ri.eu/ueabs/